

Denitrification in Sunlight and its Retardation. Part II.

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In a recent communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 67) it has been shown that nitrogen in the gaseous state is lost from soils when the conditions are favourable for oxidation on exposure to light and air.

We have observed that the loss of nitrogen on exposing ammonium salt solutions to air is always greater in light than in the dark. Solutions of ammonium chloride and sodium nitrite have been found to decompose readily with evolution of nitrogen gas when exposed to sunlight mixed with sterilised and unsterilised soils. This decomposition is considerably less in dilute solutions containing ammonium and nitrite ions and when the temperature is low. Cane-sugar has been found to be a retarder of this type of denitrification.

All these and other observations on the nitrogen loss from soils under aerobic conditions have been explained from the view point that in the processes of ammonification and nitrification taking place in the soil or in solution, ammonium nitrite is produced, which decomposes readily into nitrogen and water by increase of temperature or exposure to light. The formation of ammonium nitrite from ammonium salts or proteins requires oxygen and that is why, this type of denitrification is facilitated by increased soil aeration and also soil acidity, as nitrous acid undergoes decomposition according to the equation,

Addition of carbonaceous substances like molasses tends to preserve the soil nitrogen by decreasing the velocity of the oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil and thus decreasing the probability of the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite.

This type of denitrification observed when the soil conditions are favourable for oxidation, first studied by Lipman and Blair (*Soil Sci.*, 1921, 12, 1) and emphasised by Russel ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth," 1932, pp. 367-69) has now been satisfactorily explained by Dhar and collaborators (*Nature*, 1934, 134, 572; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 67). As this phenomenon is of very great importance specially under tropical conditions, we are continuing our researches on this

type of nitrogen loss, which may be greater in amount than the nitrogen required by a crop growing on the soil.

Our experimental results recorded in this paper can be divided into four parts, *viz.*, (1) decomposition of solutions of ammonium nitrite when exposed to artificial light, (2) nitrogen loss from mixtures of ammonium chloride and potassium nitrite when mixed with powdered soil and exposed to sunlight in the summer months, (3) loss of nitrogen when α -alanine and potassium nitrite are mixed with soil and exposed to sunlight, (4) loss of nitrogen in the gaseous state by exposing ammonium salts and nitrites in quartz vessels under sterile conditions.

Decomposition of Solutions of Ammonium Nitrite.

A solution of barium nitrite was mixed with an equivalent amount of solution of ammonium sulphate in a quartz cell and the barium sulphate allowed to settle and the solution exposed to the total light from a gas-filled tungsten filament lamp of 1000 watt. A parallel beam of light was obtained by a quartz lens. In order to keep the temperature of the solution in the quartz cell constant, a steady current of water from a thermostat was circulated. The results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

NH₃-N added as (NH₄)₂SO₄ = 0.14 g. NO₂-N added as Ba(NO₃)₂ = 0.159 g. Total N added (Devarda's) = 0.2999 g.

Treatment.	NH ₃ -N left.	NO ₂ -N left.	Total N left.	NH ₃ -N lost.	NO ₂ -N lost.	Total N lost.	% Lost.
<i>Light</i>							
Exposure at							
40° for 5 hrs.	0.133 g.	0.151 g.	0.2859 g.	0.007 g.	0.008 g.	0.014 g.	4.5
40° for 10 hrs.	0.1228	0.1414	0.2646	0.0172	0.0176	0.0353	11.7
40° for 20 hrs.	0.1028	0.1206	0.2235	0.0392	0.0384	0.0764	25.4
50° for 5 hrs.	0.1295	0.1480	0.2789	0.0105	0.011	0.021	7
50° for 10 hrs.	0.112	0.1290	0.2438	0.028	0.03	0.056	18.6
50° for 20 hrs.	0.083	0.100	0.1859	0.057	0.059	0.114	38.1
<i>Dark</i>							
Kept at							
40° for 5 hrs.	0.1388	0.1572	0.2974	0.0012	0.0018	0.0025	0.8
40° for 10 hrs.	0.1330	0.151	0.2859	0.007	0.008	0.014	4.6
40° for 20 hrs.	0.1225	0.141	0.2649	0.0175	0.018	0.035	11
50° for 5 hrs.	0.1352	0.154	0.2902	0.0048	0.005	0.0097	3.2
50° for 10 hrs.	0.1256	0.1446	0.2711	0.0144	0.0144	0.0288	9.6
50° for 20 hrs.	0.104	0.125	0.2279	0.036	0.034	0.072	24

The experimental results show that the rate of decomposition of solutions of ammonium nitrite both in light and in the dark are auto-catalytic. The velocity goes on increasing as the chemical change progresses. The pH of the solutions were also estimated before and after decomposition and no change was observed.

Many years ago Arndt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 39, 64) showed that the thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite is accelerated by acids and retarded by ammonia. A very interesting point is brought out by our researches that the ratio of the photochemical and thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite solutions at 40° is higher than the same ratio obtained at 50°. In other words, when the temperature is high, the thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite becomes quite prominent.

TABLE II.

Treatment. After	Loss of nitrogen			Percentage loss in	
	Dark and light.	Dark only.	Light only.	Dark.	Light.
5 hrs. at 40°	0·014 g.	0·0025 g.	0·0115 g.	0·8	3·8
10 hrs. at 40°	0·0353	0·014	0·0213	4·6	7·1
20 hrs. at 40°	0·0764	0·035	0·0414	11·0	13·9
5 hrs. at 50°	0·021	0·0097	0·0113	3·2	3·8
10 hrs. at 50°	0·056	0·0288	0·0272	9·6	9
20 hrs. at 50°	0·114	0·072	0·042	24	14

*Decomposition of Mixtures of Ammonium Sulphate and
Potassium Nitrite Mixed with Dry Soil.*

Powdered unsterilised garden soil was mixed with different amounts of ammonium sulphate and potassium nitrite in enamelled shallow dishes and covered with glass plates and exposed to sunlight daily for 9 hours from 9th March till 13th July 1935. No water was added in these experiments. In order to obtain comparable results in the dark, in one set of experiments the glass covers were blackened on the outside with a thick coating of Japan black enamel to cut off light and the dishes with blackened glass covers were also put in the sun in order to obtain the thermal decompositions under identical conditions. The results obtained are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III.

NH ₄ -N added.	NO ₂ -N added.	Total N added.	NH ₄ -N left.	NO ₂ -N left.	NO ₃ -N formed.	Total N left.	Total N loss.	% Loss.
<i>Light</i>								
0.5%	0.0%	0.5%	0.1809	0.0020	0.02	0.182	0.318	68.6
0.0	0.5	0.5	0.0021	0.14	0.2699	0.42	0.088	17.6
0.25	0.25	0.5	0.0312	0.14	0.021	0.192	0.308	60.1
0.4	0.1	0.5	0.0875	0.00934	0.0912	0.1881	0.3119	62.3
0.1	0.4	0.5	0.0107	0.168	0.0887	0.25	0.25	50
0.3	0.2	0.5	0.04	0.084	0.0635	0.1875	0.3125	62.5
0.2	0.3	0.5	0.018	0.0934	0.0586	0.17	0.33	66
<i>Dark</i>								
0.5	0.0	0.5	0.35	0.0002	0.0395	0.3897	0.1103	22
0.0	0.5	0.5	0.002	0.3751	0.0665	0.4444	0.0556	11
0.25	0.25	0.5	0.39	0.2012	0.0092	0.2942	0.2502	50
0.3	0.2	0.5	0.078	0.1258	0.026	0.2298	0.2752	55
0.2	0.3	0.5	0.0268	0.1489	0.035	0.2092	0.2908	58

The experimental results show that in the heat of summer months there is considerable thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite, but the decomposition in sunlight is appreciably greater than in the dark. In Allahabad in months of April, May and June the temperature in the sun goes up to 75° and hence the ammonium salts, specially the nitrite, undergo considerable decomposition even when mixed with ordinary powdered soil containing only 5.6 % moisture. Ammonium sulphate also undergoes considerable loss. The potassium nitrite when mixed with dry soil is oxidised to nitrate to a large extent and undergoes a slight loss of nitrogen probably due to the decomposition of nitrous acid formed by the action of carbonic acid on the potassium nitrite.

Nitrogen Loss from Mixtures of α -Alanine and Potassium Nitrite Mixed with Soil.

Another set of experiments was carried on by mixing α -alanine and potassium nitrite with ordinary soil and exposed to sunlight in

open beakers from 19th February to 7th March, 1935. The results in Table IV show that there is considerable loss of nitrogen even in these experiments.

TABLE IV.

Amino acid N added.	NO ₂ -N added.	Total N originally present.	NH ₃ -N left.	NO ₂ -N left.	NO ₂ -N formed.	Total N added.	Total N left Kjeldal.	% N Loss
Exposure to sunlight = 114 hours.								
0.0906%	0.1015%	0.035%	0.0204	Traces	0.00169	0.2271	0.0875	61.4
0.0906	0.203	0.035	0.1868	0.0823	0.00169	0.3296	0.0667	72.1
0.1812	0.203	0.035	0.0114	0.1270	0.08	0.35	0.1000	35.1
0.1812	0.1015	0.035	0.0175	0.0005	0.00129	0.3177	0.0778	75.3
0.0906	0.000	0.035	0.0208	0.0005	0.000	0.1256	0.1008	1.1
0.1812	0.000	0.035	0.036	0.0012	0.00164	0.2162	0.175	1.8
0.000	0.1015	0.035	0.0009	0.056	0.0454	0.1365	0.04	22.3
0.000	0.203	0.035	0.0007	0.1167	0.0862	0.238	0.0426	45.9

Amino-acid was absent at the end of these experiments as indicated by the ninhydrin reagent.

*Nitrogen Loss by Exposing to Sunlight Ammonium
Salt and a Nitrite Solution Mixed with
Soil under Sterile Conditions.*

In order to find out whether the decomposition of ammonium nitrite solution can take place under sterile conditions, the soil, the ammonium sulphate, the potassium nitrite and a silica boiling tube were sterilised in an autoclave for 2½ hours at 20 lbs. pressure. 25 C.c. of sterile distilled water were added and exposed to sunlight, the mouth of the silica boiling tube was covered with a plug of sterile cotton wool.

0.25 G. of ammoniacal nitrogen as ammonium sulphate and 0.25 g. nitric nitrogen as potassium nitrite were mixed with 50 g. sterile soil and 25 c.c. of sterile water were exposed to sunlight for 474 hours in the months of January, February and March, 1935. After this

exposure 0.056 g. of NH_3 -nitrogen and 0.0422 g. of nitric-nitrogen were left in the soil showing a decomposition of 80% of the nitrogen added. There was a steady evolution of bubbles of nitrogen gas in experiment. Hence it can be concluded that this type of denitrification can take place in the absence of bacteria.

Part played by Organic Manures.

The observations of Lipman and Blair (*Soil Sci.*, 1918, 5, 291) Clark and Rolley (*ibid.*, 1931, 31, 299) and Russell ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth", 1932, pp. 480-81) seem to indicate that farmyard manure is more effective than artificial manure in plant growth. The part played by organic substances in the soil, has been stated by Russell in the following words:—

"While plants can grow satisfactorily and attain full development with inorganic nutrients only, yet, in natural conditions, their nutrition always proceeds in presence of organic matter. There has been much discussion as to whether this plays an active part in the process.

The experimental evidence is not very definite.

In the Rothamsted field experiments, no combination of artificial fertilisers is as effective as farmyard manure in steadying crop yields from year to years, but the effect could readily be attributed to physical and physico-chemical action on the soil."

Lipman and Blair (*loc. cit.*) have stated that analysis of the soil at the end of 20 years' period show that a large part of the nitrogen not recovered from the farm manure is found accumulated in the soil, but there is no accumulation of nitrogen in the plots treated with sodium nitrate.

On the other hand, Prayanishnikov (*Trans. Sci. Inst. Fert. Moscow*, 1930, 73, 61) has concluded that the results obtained at Rothamsted, Danish and Russian experimental stations show that artificial manures are better than farmyard manure. Investigators in India notably Norris (*Mem. Dept. Agr. India, Chem. Series*, 1923, 6, No. 8) Viswanath ("Some Aspects of Plant Nutrition", 1932, pp. 13-16) Batham (private communication) and others have shown that farmyard manure is better than a complete mineral manure containing nitrogen, potash and phosphates for a long period of cultivation and that farmyard manure has a residual effect lasting for five years. We are of the opinion that besides the well known influence of organic matter in increasing the colloidal matter and water retention power

of the soil, the carbonaceous matter added to the soil with farmyard and other organic manures markedly retard the oxidation of proteins to ammonia and of ammonium salts to nitrites and nitrates.

In several publications from these laboratories (Compare Dhar "New Conceptions in Biochemistry" 1932, pp. 44-46) it has been shown, that both carbohydrates and fats markedly act as negative catalysts, and retard the oxidation of amino-acids and proteins, and that is why carbohydrates and fats are likely to act as protein sparer in the animal body. Similarly the oxidation of carbohydrates and fats is also retarded by proteins or amino-acids. These results have recently been confirmed by Ghosh and Rakshit (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 357). Moreover Willstire (*Z. Physiol.*, 1931, **72**, 88) has shown that the oxidation of adrenaline in presence of enzymes is very considerably retarded by the addition of amino-acids. In the soil also, the carbonaceous substances like cellulose, carbohydrates, fats, added with organic manure retard the oxidation of proteins, amino-acids, and ammonium salts by air and thus act as protectors of the soil nitrogen compounds. It is clear, therefore, that when the carbon content of a soil is high and the nitrogen content low, there will be less oxidation of the soil nitrogen and less chance for the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite and less nitrogen loss than when the carbon content is low and nitrogen content high. The foregoing observations, justify the application of organic manures for preserving the nitrogen of soils, specially in tropical countries, where due to sunlight and high temperature, the velocity of the oxidation of the soil organic and inorganic compounds and the decomposition of ammonium nitrite is high and the nitrogenous compounds want more protection than in temperate climates.

Molasses from sugar factories in India are practically wasted now. They should be added to the soil for the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen as has been observed by us (Compare *Proc. Acad. Sci., U. P*, 1934, **4**, 175 ; 1935, **4**, 330), and for the preservation of the soil nitrogenous compounds by decreasing their too rapid oxidation.

Sahasrabudhe and Gokhale (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1933, **2**, 68) have studied the nitrification of different oil-cakes in medium black, laterite and garden soils and have shown that nitrogen loss occurs and this loss is the greatest with the most easily and quickly nitrifiable cakes.

Heck (*Soil Sci.*, 1931, **31**, 335) has reported that in the conservation of the nitrogen in farm manure, the conditions must be anaerobic and $\frac{3}{8}$ to $\frac{1}{2}$ of the nitrogen in manure is easily lost by spreading

in warm dry and sunny days. These results are easily explained from the viewpoint advanced in these publications.

The experimental results recorded in this paper show that ammonium sulphate mixed with soil, and exposed to sunlight in the hottest part of the year decomposes to the extent of 60% and in order to minimise this nitrogen loss, which is more pronounced in tropical conditions, the ammonium salts have to be mixed with carbonaceous substances like molasses, green manure, etc. It appears that in the tropics, the value of ammonium salts as manure is enhanced when mixed with carbonaceous substances in order to decrease the velocity of the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite. Our results show that molasses not only fixes atmospheric nitrogen when added to the soil but acts as a protector of the soil nitrogen and hence it would prove to be a valuable manure specially in tropical places. Oil-cakes containing fats and nitrogenous compounds can also act in the preservation of the soil nitrogen, because fats are known to retard the oxidation of proteins and amino-acids.

SUMMARY.

1. The velocity of the thermal and photochemical decomposition of an aqueous solution of NH_4NO_2 has been determined at 40° and 50° . The velocity of the thermal decomposition is increased by increase of temperature, but the photochemical velocity is slightly affected by increase of temperature. The ratio of photochemical to the thermal decomposition of NH_4NO_2 is higher at 40° than at 50° , *i.e.*, when the temperature is high, the thermal decomposition of NH_4NO_2 is marked.

2. Copious decomposition of mixtures of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and KNO_2 in presence of dry soil and exposed to sunlight in the months of April, May and June, has been observed.

3. Solutions of α -alanine and KNO_2 mixed with soil and exposed to sunlight undergo considerable loss of nitrogen.

4. Sterile solutions of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and KNO_2 mixed with sterilised soil when exposed to sunlight in quartz boiling tubes show considerable decomposition with evolution of gaseous nitrogen.

5. Organic manures, oil-cakes, green manure, farmyard manure, molasses, etc., produce beneficial results specially in tropical countries not only by increasing the colloidal content and water retention power of the soil, but also protect the soil nitrogen by decreasing the velocity of the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite.